

LINGUISTIC UNITS CREATING THE IMAGE OF A
WOMAN IN PROSE WORKS**Xusanova Ro'zigul Berdi qizi**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18454480>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 29st January 2026Accepted: 30th January 2026Online: 31th January 2026**KEYWORDS***simile, metaphor, comparison, epithet, concept of image, linguistic unit, image of a woman***ABSTRACT**

This article examines the linguistic units that create the image of women in works of art created in the Uzbek language. Among the linguistic units, such units as simile, metaphor, comparison, epithet are analyzed. The most common types of linguistic units that create the image of women are identified.

As long as literature exists, the existence of images has been a stable phenomenon. The concept of image is the artistic expression of animate and inanimate events or feelings created by the author in the work¹.

It is known that the image of a woman is often found in poetic and prose works. It is no exaggeration to say that the image of a woman was originally created in ancient Uzbek literature as a symbol of spiritual beauty and love, as a means of depicting them².

There is a literary work that is difficult to imagine without the image of a woman. In each work, although small, the image of a woman is present, and of course, to describe and characterize this image, writers and poets resort to linguistic units. The most important of these units are: simile, comparison, epithet, metaphor, etc.

Simile: in literature, a comparison of two or more things, phenomena or characteristics based on a common similarity between them³.

Comparison: comparing the characteristics and properties of a particular object with each other⁴.

Epithet: an adjective used to vividly, vividly describe or illustrate the qualities of a thing, event, phenomenon, etc⁵.

Metaphor: transferring a similar aspect of the sign or action of one object to another, i.e., a portable meaning⁶.

The descriptions given to the image of a woman in works of art can be linguistically analyzed as follows:

In Chulpan's novel "Kecha va kunduz":

¹ Quronov D. Adabiyotshunoslik lug'ati. – Toshkent: Akademnashr, 2013. – B. 42.

² <https://linlibrary.uz>. O'zbek adabiyotida ayol obrazi.

³ <https://uz.Wikipedia.org>.

⁴ Radjabov A. Ilmiy tadqiqot asoslari. – Toshkent, 2012.

⁵ O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. 2014-2025. Izoh.uz.

⁶ Erkaboyeva N., Abdusattorova X. O'zbek tilidan ma'ruzalar to'plami. – Toshkent: Yosh kuch, 2023. – 106 b.

If we take the image of Zebi, the writer has shown how simple, beautiful, polite, and unique the female nature is.

Zebi: her face is white, her eyes are black, her eyebrows are like a bow, her hair is like black silk⁷.

Metaphor: her hair was wavy.

Simile: like a bow.

Comparison: like silk

In Abdullah Qodiriy's novel "Kecha va kunduz":

A silver image; her eyes shone like stars, her face with drawn eyebrows was white, her lips were red. Her every movement was graceful and gentle⁸.

Epithet: white, red

Metaphor: eyes like stars

Similarity: shone like stars.

In Said Ahmad's "Ufq" trilogy:

The image of Rana: her patience was like the endurance of a mountain, her love was like the warmth of a mother's heart.

Metaphor: the endurance of a mountain

Similarity: the warmth of a mother's heart.

In Shuhrat's novel "Oltin zanglamas":

Image of Aunt Adolat: She was crying with joy. When the ceremony was over, Jannat lifted Aunt Adolat by the arm, but she could not bear it, she put her head on her fragile shoulders and cried, unable to control her tears.

Metaphor: fragile shoulders.

In Otkir Hoshimov's novel "Ikki eshik orasi":

Image of Rabiya: Her thin but beautiful face was sad, and her eyes were fiery. She disturbed the heart with every glance.

Metaphor: Her eyes were fiery

Epithet: Sad.

In Said Ahmad's work "Qorakoz majnun":

Image of Qumri: She did not speak much. She was silent, but in her heart lived unspeakable sorrows. Her gaze was kind, and her voice softened the heart.

Metaphor: softening the heart.

Comparison: her gaze is kind.

In Chingiz Aitmatov's work "Sarvqomat dilbarim":

The writer describes the image of Asel as: smooth, white-faced, long, silky black hair, eyes full of kindness, slender stature, and a quiet smile.

Simile: silky.

Adjective: black hair.

Epithet: quiet smile.

Comparison: eyes full of kindness.

⁷ Cho'lon. Kecha va kunduz. – Toshkent: Sharq, 2018. – B. 25.

⁸ Abdulla Qodiriy. O'tkan kunlar. – Toshkent: Sharq, 2018. – B. 32-36.

As a result of the above analysis, it was found that linguistic units such as simile, comparison, epithet, and metaphor are actively used in the image of a woman. The study of these units provides important information for the fields of linguistics, linguoculturology, and linguopoetics.

List of used literature:

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7. Cho'lpon. Kecha va kunduz. – Toshkent: Sharq, 2018. – B. 25.
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